

Clustering of Librarians' Initial Knowledge on the Theme of Training

Klasterisasi Pengetahuan Awal Pustakawan terhadap Tema Pelatihan

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Abstract

Background of study: The implementation of librarian competency development through training in Sidenreng Rappang Regency, South Sulawesi Province, was carried out by dividing librarians based on the location of their agency's work area. In practice, there are training barriers, namely differences in absorption of the material due to limited training time and differences in initial knowledge of the training material.

Purpose: According to the librarian's prior knowledge of the training to be held in future, this study attempts to determine the best grouping and number of participants.

Method: The methodology used in this research is Cross Industry Standard Process for Data Mining (CRISP-DM) which consists of 6 stages. The data collection technique used a questionnaire with a linear numerical scale from a score of 0 to 10 to 97 librarians in Sidenreng Rappang Regency. Data were analyzed using the K-Means algorithm to determine the number of groups and the number of librarians in each group and evaluated using the Davies-Bouldin index (DBI) algorithm to determine the most optimal group division.

Findings: According to this study, the best number of groups for training in the processing of library materials is two under a DBI value of 0.68983. With a DBI value of 0.69431, the best number of groups is two in the library promotion training.

Conclusion: the library service training had the best number of groups of 2 with a DBI value of 0.65698. Meanwhile, for INLISLite-based automation training, the best number of groups is two groups with a DBI value of 0.65500.

Keywords: librarian competencies; professional development; clustering; K-Means; Davies–Bouldin Index

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A translation of “Klasterisasi Pengetahuan Awal Pustakawan terhadap Tema Pelatihan”

Data for this study are available at <https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12690/RIN/4VGCTD>

Introduction

A library is an institution that has a mandate as a means to support lifelong education. Unlike formal education, learning through a library is not limited by time or age. This lifelong learning also applies to librarians as they prepare for changes in the future. Such a learning model helps librarians to always have a fresh memory of the knowledge they have learned in the past, as well as to expand their understanding of the latest practices in libraries. Librarians who continue to learn will be sensitive to the changes that occur, enabling them to respond to the challenges that arise in their position as professionals. In addition, the rapid development of information brings forth many new things that can be studied and applied in libraries to improve service quality. In this regard, librarians need continuing education to enhance their competencies as professionals (Orme, 2008). Librarians are required to be competent professionals who are sensitive to changing trends in the field (Cooke, 2012). Furthermore, the advent of the Industry 4.0 era and even Society 5.0 has changed society's paradigm regarding information. New skills are needed by librarians in this new digital era (Raju, 2014). Librarians must adapt to the changes occurring in libraries, whether they are internal or external factors. Reflecting on this condition, enhancing librarians' skills becomes a primary concern to address the challenges of both the present and the future. The improvement of librarians' skills and knowledge is very important and aligns with the goal of providing quality services while meeting the increasing needs of users. These changes often frame the need for skills and knowledge with lifelong learning and the enhancement of professionalism (Neigel, 2017). The enhancement of knowledge for librarians can occur through formal and informal education programs, including training, technical guidance, seminars, and similar activities. These educational programs should prepare librarians to face various demands and expectations from diverse users and organizations (Davis & Saunders, 2020). Continuous education strengthens librarians' understanding of library science, often referred to as hard skills, and is complemented by good personal skills or soft skills. Knowledge that is continually honed makes librarians competent professionals in their field.

The development of librarian competencies is the responsibility of library organizers. Librarians need to be equipped with updated knowledge, skills, and abilities to adapt to changes in user needs and demands. To achieve a well-developed library, it is necessary to have competent librarians (Masruri et al., 2016). Therefore, in Indonesia, particularly at the city or district level, public libraries are given the authority to develop librarians within their working areas. The Library and Archives Service of Sidenreng Rappang Regency (Dispus Arsip Kab. Sidrap) is one of the agencies authorized to provide guidance to libraries, including their managers or librarians. In the process of this guidance, Dispus Arsip Kab. Sidrap faces challenges regarding the training methods applied. The training that has been conducted is considered not to be effective and efficient. Previously, training was carried out by dividing participants based on the domicile area of the institutions where the librarians work. This created obstacles in implementation, particularly regarding the varying levels of prior knowledge among librarians, which affected their absorption of the training material, as well as the limited training time. In practical terms, for example, technology-based training is easier to understand for librarians who already have a background in computer knowledge, allowing them to absorb and apply the material more quickly. On the other hand, librarians with limited knowledge of technology require more detailed explanations and need more time compared to the previous type of librarian. Intensive mentoring is sometimes necessary for some librarians.

Meanwhile, the field of information and communication technology plays a significant role in changing the demands for librarian professionals (Raju, 2014). This implies that attention must be given to knowledge equity among librarians after participating in an educational program. Additionally, when designing an educational program, the background of a librarian's abilities is one of the aspects that need to be considered (Brown et al., 2015; Masruri et al., 2016). Attention to the knowledge possessed by librarians before training is expected to help participants achieve the same educational goals after the program concludes. The educational programs organized should be tailored to the knowledge patterns already possessed by librarians, including the needs, conditions, and uniqueness of the Sidenreng Rappang Regency, whether conducted face-to-face or online. The planned competency development program for librarians at Dispus Arsip Kab. Sidenreng Rappang includes the processing of library materials, library promotion, library services, and automation based on INLISLite.

Based on this, the aim of this research is to find the best grouping and the number of participants in each group based on the basic knowledge of librarians regarding the training sessions that will be held. Participants are not grouped based on the region of the institution where the librarians work, but rather based on the participants' background knowledge, with the hope of producing training that is more effective and efficient in its implementation, thereby achieving equivalent educational outcomes.

Methodology

The methodology used in this research is the Cross-Industry Standard Process for Data Mining (CRISP-DM). CRISP-DM is a standard process model for implementing data mining projects that consists of 6 phases (Schröer et al., 2021). The steps in CRISP-DM include business understanding, data understanding, data preparation, modeling, evaluation, and deployment.

The data collection technique used a questionnaire with a linear numeric scale from 0 to 10, targeting 97 librarians in Sidenreng Rappang Regency. The questionnaire consists of 20 statements divided into 4 training themes, with each training theme containing 5 statements. Each statement has a score range from 0 to 10, where 0 indicates that the respondent is very incapable or has a very poor understanding of a concept. Meanwhile, a score of 10 indicates that the respondent is very capable or has a very good understanding of the proposed concept. The total population taken is all the librarians recorded by the Dispus Arsip Kab. Sidenreng Rappang, as the aim of this research is to group all existing librarians.

The data from the questionnaire was then analyzed using the K-Means algorithm to determine the number of groups and the number of librarians in each group. K-Means is an algorithm with a simple iterative method for partitioning a dataset according to the number of clusters or groups specified by the user (Wu et al., 2008). This algorithm groups each data point based on its proximity to the cluster center or centroid (Rokach & Maimon, 2005). The number of groups is determined manually according to the number of groups to be tested. In this study, grouping trials were conducted from 2 groups to 6 groups for each training theme, and the number of participants in each group was observed. The variable to be grouped is the score of each librarian's statements regarding the centroid.

The formed groups or clusters are then evaluated using the Davies-Bouldin Index (DBI) algorithm to determine the most optimal group division. DBI maximizes the distance between

groups while minimizing the distance between points within the same cluster (Mughnyanti et al., 2020). Each grouping of 2 to 6 groups for each training session is evaluated with DBI, and the DBI values are compared to find the smallest value. The smallest DBI value represents the best result from the formed groups (Vergani & Binaghi, 2018). The grouping using K-Means and evaluation using DBI in this study was assisted by the RapidMiner software.

Results and Discussion

Business Understanding

The initial step in CRISP-DM is to understand the business objectives and identify key factors (Chapman et al., 2000). This research was conducted to find the best grouping method for each training session in Sidenreng Rappang Regency, with the grouped factor being the librarians' prior knowledge of the training themes to be organized by the Dispus Arsip Kab. Sidenreng Rappang.

Data Understanding

The next phase is to understand the data needed, specifically the level of knowledge of the librarians regarding the training themes. In this phase, it is necessary to establish the data sources and the method of data collection (Schröer et al., 2021). Data was obtained from a questionnaire distributed to all librarians in Sidenreng Rappang Regency through an electronic form, resulting in a total of 102 entries. This data was then processed into 4 files according to the number of training themes, with each file containing 103 rows and 6 columns. The first column represents the identity of the librarians, which is not processed but serves as a data label, while the first row contains the identity/description of each column. For further examination, the data can be visualized with graphs according to its characteristics (Chapman et al., 2000).

Figure 1. Initial Knowledge Data of Librarians on Training Themes (source: research data)

Using a box-plot graph, it can be seen that all statements have a maximum value of 10, but the minimum values appear to differ, with 9 statements having a minimum value of 1 while 11 other statements have a value of 0. This graph indicates that there is no data with values outside the defined range of 0 to 10. Sequentially, it represents the box-plot of 102 values from each of the 20 statements. The red color represents data from the training theme on library materials processing, the black color represents the library promotion theme, the blue color represents data from the library service theme, and the green color represents data on the INLISLite-based automation theme.

Data Preparation

In this phase, the collected data is identified to produce quality data before analysis. To obtain quality data, data cleaning can be performed (Chapman et al., 2000). Four files were obtained and carefully examined, revealing 5 duplicate entries in each file. It was found that several librarians had entered duplicate data. The handling of duplicate data involved retaining the most recent entry and eliminating outdated entries. A total of 5 outdated entries were eliminated, resulting in 97 entries from the original 102 entries defined in the previous stage.

Figure 2. Final Data After Cleaning (source: research data)

The changes that occurred after data cleaning are as follows: in statement number 9, the minimum value changed to 1. In statements number 3 and 4, the first quartile, which was previously 4, changed to 4.5. In statement number 8, there was a movement where the first quartile is valued at 5 and the median data became 7. Other changes occurred in statements number 10, 12, 18, and 20.

Modeling

The model used to cluster librarians in this research is the K-Means method using the RapidMiner application. The cleaned data was then imported into the application, and the data attributes were determined, with the name column used as an ID since the name column will

not be processed but will serve as the identity of the data entry. The numeric values from 0 to 10 from 5 statements in each theme were arranged into subsets using the Select Attributes operator so that this data could be processed using K-Means. To perform clustering, the K-Means operator was used with parameter K values corresponding to the number of groups to be formed; in this case, the tested K values range from 2 to 6, resulting in 5 required K-Means operators. A value of 2 means that the existing data will be divided into 2 groups based on the proximity of the data to the centroid or central point of the data. Similarly, a value of 6 will divide the data into 6 groups. The type of measurement used is Numerical Measures because the values to be calculated for distance are of numeric data type, with the calculation option being Euclidean Distance. Additionally, the Multiply operator was added to duplicate the data for distribution to other operators. Sequentially, the data is connected with the Select Attributes operator, which is then linked to the Multiply operator, allowing the data to be duplicated for forwarding to the 5 K-Means operators.

Table 1. Comparison of the Number of Librarians at Each K Value with the Theme of Library Material Processing Training

Number of Clusters (K)	Number of Librarians in Each Cluster					
	Cluster 0	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4	Cluster 5
K = 2	50	47	-	-	-	-
K = 3	27	40	30	-	-	-
K = 4	31	40	3	23	-	-
K = 5	25	21	24	2	25	-
K = 6	13	24	17	24	16	3

Source: research data

Table 2. Comparison of the Number of Librarians at Each K Value with the Theme of Library Promotion Training

Number of Clusters (K)	Number of Librarians in Each Cluster					
	Cluster 0	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4	Cluster 5
K = 2	59	38	-	-	-	-
K = 3	37	47	13	-	-	-
K = 4	33	13	28	23	-	-
K = 5	28	17	5	21	26	-
K = 6	5	13	16	28	18	17

Source: research data

Table 3. Comparison of the Number of Librarians at Each K Value with the Theme of Library Service Training

Number of Clusters (K)	Number of Librarians in Each Cluster					
	Cluster 0	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4	Cluster 5
K = 2	65	32	-	-	-	-
K = 3	29	59	9	-	-	-
K = 4	26	47	18	6	-	-
K = 5	29	20	6	16	26	-
K = 6	33	6	23	13	5	17

Source: research data

Table 4. Comparison of the Number of Librarians at Each K Value with the Theme of INLISLite-Based Automation Training

Number of Clusters (K)	Number of Librarians in Each Cluster					
	Cluster 0	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4	Cluster 5
K = 2	56	41	-	-	-	-
K = 3	28	33	36	-	-	-
K = 4	28	11	33	25	-	-
K = 5	31	25	14	11	16	-
K = 6	14	27	11	21	8	16

Source: research data

The grouping of each training theme resulted in varying values depending on the proximity to the data center point. It can be seen that some clusters have a smaller group size compared to others. For example, in the theme of library material processing training, with the group divided into 5, cluster 3 only has 2 members while other clusters have more than 20 members. Therefore, an evaluation is needed to determine the best group formation using the Davies-Bouldin Index. The numbers in the clusters are not ordinal but merely serve as labels to distinguish the identity of each cluster. To see the ranking of each formed cluster, it can be analyzed through data visualization using RapidMiner software.

Evaluation

To determine the effective groups among the values of 2 to 6, an evaluation of each formed group needs to be conducted. This step is useful for assessing the extent to which the established model meets the predetermined business objectives (Chapman et al., 2000). To perform the evaluation, the Cluster Distance Performance operator was added to the RapidMiner application, which functions to evaluate the formed groups using parameters based on the main criterion, which is the Davies Bouldin index. Five Cluster Distance Performance operators are paired one-to-one with each of the five K-Means operators.

Table 5. Results of Cluster Evaluation on the Theme of Library Materials Processing Training

Number of clusters (K)	DBI score
K = 2	0.68983
K = 3	0.87901
K = 4	0.77394
K = 5	0.84430
K = 6	0.91757

Source: research data

Table 6. Results of Cluster Evaluation on the Theme of Library Promotion Training

Number of clusters (K)	DBI score
K = 2	0.69431
K = 3	0.74646
K = 4	0.85026
K = 5	0.88149
K = 6	1.03036

Source: research data

Table 7. Results of Cluster Evaluation on the Theme of Library Service Training

Number of clusters (K)	DBI score
K = 2	0.65698
K = 3	0.70041
K = 4	0.70556
K = 5	0.80152
K = 6	0.92255

Source: research data

Table 8. Results of Cluster Evaluation on the Theme of INLISLite-Based Automation Training

Number of clusters (K)	DBI score
K = 2	0.65500
K = 3	0.67705
K = 4	0.67180
K = 5	0.81806
K = 6	0.72094

Source: research data

Dissemination

The final step in the CRISP-DM methodology is to summarize the results of the process that has been carried out, as well as the important experiences gained. At this stage, there is at least one final report on the results obtained, along with a defined plan that can be implemented (Chapman et al., 2000). The report includes a list of librarians in each training cluster and the results of the data processing, which are submitted to Dispus Arsip Kab. Sidenreng Rappang as a basis for organizing the development of librarian competencies in its working area.

Conclusion

The results of the study indicate that for the training on library materials processing, the best number of groups is 2, with a DBI value of 0.68983. The highest initial understanding level is found in cluster 0, which includes 50 librarians, while 47 librarians are in the lower cluster. In the library promotion training, the best number of groups is also 2, with a DBI value of 0.69431, where the highest initial understanding level is held by cluster 0 with 59 librarians, and 38 librarians are in cluster 1. Furthermore, in the library service training, the best number of groups is again 2, with a DBI value of 0.65698, where cluster 0 has a higher initial understanding level with 65 librarians, and 32 librarians are in the next cluster. Meanwhile, for the automation training based on INLISLite, the best number of groups is 2, with a DBI value of 0.65500, and cluster 0 is the group with the best initial understanding of the training theme, totaling 56 librarians, while 41 librarians are in cluster 1.

Further research on the effectiveness of the training model by dividing participants based on their initial knowledge is necessary to determine the success level in material absorption. There is also an opportunity to apply clustering models or other evaluation methods besides the Davies-Bouldin Index to similar cases. Additionally, this research relies on the existing population, as any increase in population will change all cluster calculations, thus requiring attention to the number of librarians and library managers in Sidenreng Rappang Regency, and a recalculation is needed if there are new hires or additions of librarians.

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